

AM4BAT PROJECT

Deliverable 5.2

Report on tailored current collectors for anode-free system

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Current collector
CE	coulombic efficiency
CNF	Carbon Nanofiber
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
FDE	First Discharge Efficiency
FTIR	Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy
GA	Grant Agreement
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LIB	Lithium-ion battery
MS	Milestone
NMR	nuclear magnetic resonance
PC	Project Coordinator
PPFS	poly(pentafluorostyrene)
SOC	state-of-charge
TM	Technical Manager
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	life-cycle analysis

1. Executive summary

Work package (WP5) has been dedicated to the development and evaluation of advanced current collectors (CC) and protective coatings for lithium metal anodes, with the overarching goal of enabling high-energy-density, safe, and durable cells for solid-state and liquid electrolyte systems. The activities carried out span across three main tasks: T5.1 (metal-coated Cu foils), T5.2 (3D carbon nanofiber mats), and T5.3 (polymeric protective layers).

The program initially started with lab-scale processing of metal-coated Cu foils (Deliverable 5.1), with a strong emphasis on Ag@Cu, as these materials quickly demonstrated superior performance in terms of surface morphology, lithium plating/stripping behavior, and cycle stability compared to Sn@Cu and other approaches. Ag coatings produced rough, high-surface-area textures that promoted lithium affinity and stability, which translated into favorable cycling metrics. Consequently, the first phase of WP5 centered largely on Ag@Cu.

However, feedback from WP8 on life-cycle analysis (LCA) highlighted the limitations of silver in terms of cost and environmental footprint. In response, the consortium placed significant effort on improving Sn@Cu foils, which, despite showing initially lower performance, offer greater industrial viability and sustainability. This shift guided the second half of WP5, where post-treatment strategies were introduced to enhance Sn@Cu surface regularity, reduce uncontrolled roughness, and improve electrochemical performance. These modifications effectively increased discharge efficiency, improved voltage plateaus, and extended cycle life, narrowing the gap between Sn@Cu and Ag@Cu.

In the current reporting period, two complementary paths were pursued. On one hand, Ag@Cu cycling was continued beyond PR1, extending from ~900 cycles into the thousands, to benchmark its ultimate durability and assess how far this material could push KPI2 targets. On the other hand, the main focus shifted to Sn@Cu, with detailed analysis of nucleation behavior, roughness before and after post-treatment, thickness uniformity (measured across six positions per sample), and full electrochemical evaluation under both low and high C-rates. These studies demonstrated that post-treated Sn@Cu achieves much higher first-discharge efficiency and presents more defined voltage plateaus during cycling, an aspect particularly relevant for state-of-charge (SOC) estimation in WP6. Importantly, Sn coatings also benefit from smoother nucleation profiles, which promote dense lithium deposition and reduce dendritic growth risks.

Parallel exploration efforts were conducted in T5.2 (3D-CNFs) and T5.3 (polymeric protective layers). CNFs synthesized from PAN with ZnO or PVP sacrificial pyrogens achieved high porosity and lithiophilicity but suffered from poor mechanical robustness and high interfacial resistance under cycling. Similarly, fluorinated PPFS-based polymers explored in T5.3 showed limited grafting efficiency and stability, despite various synthetic strategies. As a result, both approaches, while scientifically valuable, were deprioritized compared to the more scalable and industrially relevant metal-coated foils.

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In conclusion, WP5 has converged on Ni/Ag@Cu and Ni/Sn@Cu as the most promising anode CCs, with Ag@Cu serving as the high-performance reference and Sn@Cu emerging as a scalable, sustainable alternative after significant optimization. Both materials are thinner than conventional graphite electrodes, uniform, and compatible with industrial processing, enabling substantial volume savings and improved energy density at the cell level. They have been selected and delivered to WP6 and WP7 for full-cell assembly and integration. This represents an important milestone (MS7), ensuring WP5 contributes directly to meeting project KPIs on both energy density (KPI1) and cycle stability (KPI2), while also aligning with sustainability criteria identified by WP8.

2. Introduction

With the widespread adoption of portable electronics, electric vehicles, and renewable energy storage systems, the demand for rechargeable batteries with both high energy density and extended cycle life has grown significantly. Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) currently dominate the market for these applications due to their mature technology and robust performance. However, conventional LIBs are approaching their theoretical energy density limits. One key bottleneck lies in the anode, which is almost exclusively graphite-based, offering a limited specific capacity of $372 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. To substantially enhance energy density at the cell level, new anode materials with higher capacity and long-term stability must be developed.

Lithium (Li) metal is widely considered the most promising next-generation anode material. With an ultrahigh theoretical specific capacity ($3860 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and the lowest electrochemical potential (-3.040 V vs. standard hydrogen electrode), Li metal electrodes enable batteries to reach a specific energy of $\sim 350 \text{ Wh}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, compared to today's commercial LIBs with graphite anodes ($150\text{--}250 \text{ Wh}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). Despite these advantages, commercialization of Li-metal batteries (LMBs) has been hindered by critical challenges, particularly the uncontrolled growth of Li dendrites, which compromise safety and lead to rapid capacity fade. Furthermore, the high reactivity of Li metal increases manufacturing complexity and costs, such as the need for specialized dry-room facilities.

An alternative concept that has gained momentum in recent years is the anode-free (or anode-less) configuration, in which no active material is present on the CC during cell assembly. Instead, metallic Li is electrochemically deposited on the CC during the first charge cycle. On discharge, Li is stripped back to the cathode, theoretically restoring the CC to its pristine state. While the gravimetric energy density of anode-free cells is comparable to that of LMBs due to the low density of Li metal ($0.534 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$), the volumetric energy density can exceed $1000 \text{ Wh}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, far outperforming both graphite-based LIBs ($250\text{--}500 \text{ Wh}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and conventional LMBs ($\sim 750 \text{ Wh}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$).

However, several technical hurdles remain before anode-free batteries can be realized at scale:

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1. Lithiophilicity of the current collector: The CC must promote uniform Li nucleation and deposition, requiring minimal nucleation overpotential. Conventional copper CCs used in LIBs are not sufficiently lithiophilic.
2. Reversibility of Li plating/stripping: Achieving high coulombic efficiency (CE) is essential for long cycle life. CE, defined as the ratio of extracted charge to input charge during a cycle, directly reflects the stability and reversibility of Li deposition.

In Work Package 5 (WP5), the focus is on developing advanced anode concepts aligned with KPI1 & 2 of the project: increasing energy density at the cell level while maintaining competitive cycle life. Task 5.1 (T5.1): Anode-Free Concept: The objective is to engineer a highly lithiophilic CC, thinner than conventional graphite electrodes, to enhance energy density. The target is to achieve at least comparable capacity to graphite while significantly improving cycle life. Task 5.2 (T5.2): CNF Anodes: Carbon nanofiber (CNF)-based anodes are being explored as a complementary strategy, offering higher surface area and enhanced Li storage capability. Task 5.3 (T5.3): Artificial SEI Layers: Development of polymeric artificial solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) coatings on Li foil is underway to stabilize Li-metal surfaces and suppress dendrite growth.

In Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1), the foundations of the anode-free and alternative anode approaches were established. Building on this, D5.2 focused on lab-scale testing of the proposed anode concepts, providing critical experimental validation. Within this deliverable, particular attention was given to scalability (OB3), evaluating not only technical performance but also the potential for upscaling beyond the laboratory environment. In addition, LCA results from WP8 were integrated as key decision parameters, ensuring that the final outcome of WP5 reflects not only performance but also considerations of scalability and long-term sustainability. Taken together, these approaches aim to overcome the key limitations of graphite and Li-metal anodes, moving closer to practical and commercially viable high-energy-density batteries.

3. Objectives

The objective of this WP in general is to advance the anode-less lithium-based battery concept by developing a thin, lithiophilic CC that enables stable Li plating and stripping with high CE and limited dendrite formation. This work aims to overcome the limitations of graphite and Li-metal anodes, enabling higher energy density, improved cycle life, and safer operation without pre-assembled metallic lithium. In addition to technical performance, the deliverable incorporates scalability and sustainability considerations to support future industrial adoption. The overall objective of this WP is to develop a CC that enables the Li plating/stripping with high CE and limited dendrite formation.

The specific objectives of WP5 are:

- To reach 80% of the initial capacity at 1C for at least 3000 cycles
- To develop stable anode up to 5 mAh cm⁻², demonstrated by stripping plating test in half-cell

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- To upscale the anode-less concept and lithophilic current collector for manufacturing of 20 units 3Ah cell.

Whether these objectives have been successfully achieved or partially met will be discussed in detail in the **conclusion section** of this report.

4. Methodology

The development of lithophilic CC in Task 5.1 was based on the modification of commercial copper foils through a combination of surface preparation, metallic underlayer deposition, and secondary metallization. The purpose of this approach was to create controlled nanostructured surfaces that can act as preferential nucleation sites for lithium, thereby ensuring uniform plating and stripping and reducing the risk of dendrite growth.

The process began with a cleaning and micro-etching stage, designed to remove surface oxides and contaminants while also roughening the copper substrate. This step is essential to provide sufficient adhesion and ensure intimate contact between the copper and the subsequently deposited metallic layers.

Following this, a nickel underlayer was electrochemically deposited. Nickel was selected due to its stability, good conductivity, and ability to act as an intermediate layer that promotes strong bonding between the copper substrate and the top functional layer. The thickness and uniformity of this nickel film are critical, as they directly influence current distribution during cycling.

A secondary metallic coating was then applied, using either silver (Ag) or tin (Sn). These metals were chosen because of their higher affinity toward lithium compared to bare copper, making them more lithophilic substrates. By modifying the surface chemistry in this way, lithium ions are more likely to deposit uniformly across the CC rather than forming localized, dendritic structures.

Finally, a subset of samples underwent additional surface modification treatments, aimed at further optimizing surface energy and improving the wetting properties for lithium deposition. While the specific chemistries are confidential, these treatments were designed to tune the surface-electrolyte interface and to minimize nucleation overpotential during the first cycles.

Overall, this methodology produced four main variants: Cu foil/Ni/Ag (Ag@Cu), Cu foil/Ni/Sn (Sn@Cu) each with and without surface modification. Each foil was prepared on both its shiny and matt sides, enabling systematic evaluation of the influence of initial substrate morphology. These processed foils, together with pure copper foil used as a baseline reference, form the experimental set for subsequent electrochemical testing. In these tests, plating/stripping efficiency, CE, and cycle stability will be systematically evaluated to assess the effectiveness of the modified CCs compared to unmodified Cu.

The methodology for Task 5.2 builds on the work already reported in Deliverable 5.1, where the synthesis and characterization of carbon nanofibers (CNFs) were described in detail. In brief, the process involves three key stages: (i) electrospinning of polymeric nanofibers from precursor solutions, (ii) stabilization of the as-spun nanofibers in air, and (iii) high-temperature carbonization under

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inert atmosphere to obtain conductive carbon nanofibers with controlled nanostructure and porosity.

For doped CNFs, precursor solutions were prepared by incorporating suitable additives into the polymer matrix before electrospinning, enabling improved conductivity and lithium affinity. The resulting fibers were subsequently subjected to stabilization and thermal treatment, leading to partial graphitization depending on the applied conditions.

These CNFs have been thoroughly characterized in terms of their structure, composition (ICP-MS), porosity (BET analysis), and electrochemical performance (lithium intercalation/deintercalation behavior). The detailed processing parameters and experimental results are already presented in Deliverable 5.1 and are not repeated here. Instead, this deliverable focuses on the use of these CNFs for further evaluation.

In Task 5.3, the focus was on the development of polymer-based protective coatings designed to stabilize lithium-metal surfaces and improve their interfacial

Figure 1 Schematic process flow of MKS | Atotech for preparation of metallic nanostructured CCs based on Cu/Ni/Ag (left) and Cu/Ni/Sn (right). The general sequence involves substrate cleaning, surface activation, deposition of a nickel underlayer, followed by a secondary metallic coating (Ag or Sn), and optional surface modification. Certain intermediate and post-treatment steps are intentionally not disclosed in this public report for confidentiality reasons.

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performance. The approach was based on the chemical modification of poly(pentafluorostyrene) (PPFS), which was functionalized through sulfonamide grafting routes to generate single-ion conducting polymers with tunable grafting densities. Different synthesis protocols were explored by varying solvents, catalysts, temperatures, and reaction durations, in order to control the degree of functionalization and obtain materials with reproducible properties suitable for electrochemical use.

The obtained polymers were extensively characterized to verify their structural and chemical integrity. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to confirm the presence of grafted functional groups, while nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy provided further insight into the chemical environment and allowed an estimation of grafting levels. These techniques, together with complementary physicochemical assessments, ensured that the functionalized polymers were well defined before use in coating experiments.

The protective coatings were applied to lithium metal by a dip-coating procedure carried out under inert atmosphere. Lithium foils were immersed into polymer solutions prepared in suitable solvents and containing a defined polymer concentration. After immersion, the foils were dried under vacuum to remove residual solvent and to ensure that a uniform, adherent polymeric film covered the lithium surface.

The coated electrodes were then assembled into symmetric Li|Li cells to allow systematic evaluation of their interfacial behavior. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was used to monitor the resistance evolution at the electrode/electrolyte interface, while galvanostatic cycling at controlled current densities was employed to study plating and stripping stability over extended times. All experiments were conducted in carefully controlled inert conditions to minimize side reactions and ensure reproducibility.

5. Results

5.1. 3D-metallic nanostructured and lithiophilic current collector [LEITAT, VUB] M1-M36.

5.1.1. Surface Roughness of Sn@Cu and Ag@Cu

Figure 2 presents representative images of two metallized copper foils, each measuring approximately 9 × 6 cm, coated under identical processing conditions but with different lithiophilic top layers. On the left, the foil is coated with silver (Ni/Ag), while on the right, the foil is coated with tin (Ni/Sn).

Figure 2 Representative metallized copper foils (~9 × 6 cm) coated with Ni/Ag (left) and Ni/Sn (right). The silver coating appears bright and reflective, while the tin coating is duller and more textured, reflecting differences in surface morphology and coating.

The Ag@Cu sample displays a bright, highly reflective surface, characteristic of Ag films. The uniform appearance suggests good coverage and smooth deposition, which is advantageous for lowering nucleation overpotentials during lithium plating. The metallic sheen indicates that the coating is compact and continuous, providing a surface expected to promote homogeneous lithium nucleation.

In contrast, the tin-coated sample exhibits a duller, matte appearance with visible texturing across the surface. This less reflective finish indicates a rougher surface morphology, potentially arising from grain boundaries and localized variations in deposition thickness. Such features are expected to influence electrochemical behavior: while Sn provides alloying capacity with lithium, the granular surface could act as preferential nucleation sites, potentially leading to less uniform Li deposition compared to Ag.

This comparison highlights the contrasting surface characteristics of Ag and Sn as lithiophilic coatings. Silver provides a smoother and more reflective interface, favorable for uniform lithium growth, while tin offers alloying capability but results in a rougher coating morphology. Both approaches will be further evaluated electrochemically to assess their influence on CE, reversibility, and dendrite suppression in anode-less cell configurations.

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The surface roughness of the coated foils was evaluated by SEM and AFM, as shown in Figure 3. Sn@Cu samples exhibited smoother and more compact morphologies, with moderate roughness, whereas Ag@Cu samples showed a rougher texture with sharp peaks and valleys, leading to higher surface area but reduced uniformity. Such differences are clearly visible in the AFM maps, where the Ag coating presents irregular topography compared to the more even Sn surface.

Figure 3 AFM analysis of Sn@Cu and Ag@Cu coatings without post-treatment, showing smoother Sn surfaces and rougher Ag surfaces with sharp peaks and valleys.

When post-treatments were applied (Figure 4), a marked improvement in surface homogeneity was observed. Sn@Cu post treated showed a denser, more leveled structure, while Ag@Cu post treated displayed reduced roughness and a more uniform distribution of surface features compared to the untreated foils. These morphological refinements are expected to lower local current variations, reduce the likelihood of dendritic lithium growth, and improve plating/stripping reversibility.

The roughness and thickness of the processed CC foils were analyzed after metallization and subsequent heat treatment, providing important insights into their suitability as substrates for anode-less lithium deposition. Measurements were performed at six different points across each sample (top and bottom surfaces, three points each) to ensure reliable averaging and to capture possible inhomogeneities in coating deposition, as summarized in Figure 4.

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Figure 4 Roughness measurements of Ni-, Ag-, and Sn-coated Cu foils performed at six positions (three on the top and three on the bottom surface) for both shiny and rough substrates. Average roughness values (R_a) are reported in μm . Sn@Cu coatings show relatively smooth and compact surfaces, while Ag@Cu exhibits higher roughness with more granular morphology. Representative AFM images of Sn@Cu (left) and Ag@Cu (right) illustrate the difference in surface texture.

For Ni-coated foils, the average roughness was the lowest ($\sim 2.8\text{--}4.3 \mu\text{m}$ depending on substrate side), indicating a compact and smooth layer. In contrast, Ag- and Sn-coated foils displayed higher roughness values ($\sim 9.6\text{--}11.1 \mu\text{m}$), with Sn exhibiting slightly more consistent textures than Ag. AFM images confirm these findings: Sn@Cu after post treatment showed a relatively flat and compact morphology, while Ag@Cu after post treatment retained a more granular texture, though post-treatment clearly improved homogeneity compared to the untreated foils. Heat treatment further contributed to densification, lowering local roughness variations and improving coating stability.

Thickness analysis indicated a uniform distribution across the six measured positions. A typical single-side metallized foil reached approximately $24 \mu\text{m}$, while double-sided coatings yielded $\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$ in total. Compared to conventional electrodes, this represents a 60% reduction in volume relative to lithium foils and more than 100% savings compared to graphite anodes. At the cell level, these improvements correspond to an estimated 20–30% increase in energy density, depending on the areal capacity and electrode length.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the combined control of roughness, uniform thickness, and post-treatment enables the preparation of robust, lithiophilic CCs. The improved morphological homogeneity is expected to

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suppress uneven Li deposition, while the reduced thickness directly contributes to KPI1 of the AM4BAT project.

5.1.2. Cycling Performance:

In the first reporting period (PR1), the Ag@Cu electrode demonstrated stable cycling for approximately 900 hours, confirming its suitability as a lithiophilic CC under moderate current densities. To further assess its long-term stability and to evaluate progress toward KPI2, the experiment was continued beyond the PR1 timeframe.

The extended cycling tests revealed that the Ag@Cu electrodes could sustain stable lithium plating/stripping for up to 3000 hours. Importantly, the voltage profiles remained narrow, with only minor polarization increase over time, indicating minimal resistance build-up and stable interfacial properties. This extended stability highlights the beneficial role of the Ag coating in homogenizing lithium deposition, thereby reducing dendritic growth and suppressing interfacial degradation. Overall, the continuation of testing beyond PR1 allowed the project to demonstrate that Ag@Cu electrodes can meet the requirements of KPI2, namely extended cycling with high coulombic efficiency. This confirms Ag@Cu as a reliable benchmark material, even though later work in this WP focused more on Sn@Cu to address sustainability and life-cycle considerations raised by WP8.

Figure 5 Cycling performance of Ag@Cu versus Li metal in coin cell configuration at 0.4 mA/cm² (blue) and 0.8 mA/cm² (red).

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Figure 6 shows the long-term Li plating/stripping of the thin Sn-coated Cu current collector, where the cell often reaches high overpotentials and is repeatedly stopped by the safety voltage limit. These large, irregular voltage excursions indicate unstable interfacial behavior and non-uniform Li plating/stripping, rather than fully stable cycling.

Figure 6 Cycling performance of Ag@Cu versus Li metal at 0.4 mA/cm^2

5.1.3. Nucleation and plating behavior

To further evaluate the lithiophilicity of the prepared CCs, nucleation overpotential measurements were carried out during the initial stages of lithium deposition. This test is particularly important because the nucleation overpotential directly reflects the energetic barrier for lithium nucleation on a given surface, which in turn governs how uniform the first Li nuclei are distributed. A lower nucleation overpotential is generally associated with easier Li nucleation and a higher density of smaller nuclei, while a higher overpotential typically results in fewer but larger nuclei and less uniform growth.

The results clearly distinguish the behavior of Sn@Cu, Ag@Cu, and bare Cu substrates. As can be seen from Figure 7, Sn@Cu exhibited the lowest overpotential ($\sim 205 \text{ mV}$), confirming its high lithiophilicity and tendency to facilitate rapid nucleation. This leads to the formation of a large number of small lithium nuclei, which can cover the surface more homogeneously and reduce the risk of localized dendrite initiation. Ag@Cu showed a slightly higher overpotential ($\sim 285 \text{ mV}$), indicating a somewhat greater barrier for nucleation. However, once

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nucleation occurs, Ag provides stable plating, characterized by fewer but larger nuclei. This behavior can be advantageous for maintaining stable lithium deposition in extended cycling, even if the initial nucleation density is lower than for Sn. By contrast, bare Cu displayed the highest overpotential (~ 310 mV), confirming its poor lithiophilicity and strong tendency toward heterogeneous Li growth and dendritic formation.

Figure 7 Nucleation and plating behavior of Sn@Cu, Ag@Cu, and bare Cu electrodes during initial lithium deposition, highlighting differences in nucleation overpotential.

These findings emphasize that both Sn and Ag coatings markedly reduce the nucleation barrier compared to untreated Cu, but in different ways: Sn favors a high nucleation density with smaller nuclei, while Ag promotes fewer but more stable nucleation sites. Together, these results highlight why lithiophilic surface engineering is a key strategy for enabling uniform lithium plating and improved cycling stability in anode-less battery designs.

5.1.4. Electrochemical Charge–Discharge Behavior: Effect of Post-Treatment

The charge/discharge profiles of the Sn@Cu electrodes highlight the impact of the post-treatment step on electrochemical reversibility and stability of lithium plating/stripping.

In the untreated Sn@Cu (Figure 8), the first lithiation process delivers an areal capacity of ~ 2.57 mAh·cm⁻², but the delithiation recovers only ~ 1.19 mAh·cm⁻², resulting in a first discharge efficiency (FDE) of 46%. Such low reversibility is indicative of extensive side reactions, most likely due to non-uniform nucleation and growth of lithium, the formation of “dead” lithium, and parasitic consumption of electrolyte during the first plating process. The voltage profile in this case

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shows a largely sloping behavior during both charge and discharge, without a clearly defined plateau. This suggests that lithium is deposited in an inhomogeneous manner, creating local hotspots of high current density and irregular interfaces, which in turn destabilize the SEI. For practical application, this is problematic: the absence of a reproducible and flat voltage plateau complicates SOC tracking and makes it difficult to implement reliable battery management strategies.

Figure 8 charge–discharge curve of Sn@Cu before post-treatment, showing low first discharge efficiency (46%) and sloping voltage profile, indicative of parasitic reactions and unstable Li plating/stripping.

By contrast, the post-treated Sn@Cu (Figure 9) demonstrates a marked improvement in both capacity retention and voltage profile definition. Here, the first lithiation reaches $\sim 4.1 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, and the delithiation recovers $\sim 2.6 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, corresponding to an FDE of 66%. This is a significant leap forward in terms of reversibility and demonstrates that the post-treatment enhances surface uniformity and stabilizes the interfacial chemistry. From a mechanistic standpoint, this improvement can be linked to a reduction in uncontrolled side reactions and to more homogeneous lithium nucleation across the surface. The most striking feature is the emergence of a well-defined discharge plateau at $\sim 0.2\text{--}0.3 \text{ V}$ vs. Li/Li^+ . This plateau indicates that the plating/stripping processes are no longer dominated by resistive losses and irregular SEI breakdown but instead proceed through more stable and energetically consistent interfacial reactions.

The importance of this voltage plateau extends beyond fundamental electrochemistry. In practical battery systems, especially when moving toward large-format cells and modules, a clear and reproducible plateau is critical for SOC estimation and diagnostics. Unlike sloping

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Figure 9 Charge–discharge profile of Sn@Cu after post-treatment, demonstrating improved first discharge efficiency (66%), higher areal capacity, and the emergence of a stable voltage plateau around 0.2–0.3 V (during charge) and 0.5–0.6 V (during discharge) vs. Li/Li⁺

curves, which make it difficult to determine the state of the electrode at a given voltage, flat and well-defined regions allow battery management systems (BMS) to estimate SOC with much greater accuracy. This is highly relevant to WP6, where system-level integration, monitoring, and energy management strategies will be developed. The improved behavior of post-treated Sn@Cu therefore has a direct impact on the feasibility of scaling up anode-less concepts for commercial applications.

When these results are compared to conventional graphite anodes, the contrast becomes even clearer. Graphite electrodes typically exhibit first-cycle efficiencies around 85–90% due to the well-understood formation of a stable SEI on graphite particles. However, graphite suffers from severe limitations in terms of achievable areal capacity ($\sim 3 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ practical limit) and volumetric energy density. In contrast, Sn@Cu foils, especially after post-treatment, demonstrate the potential to reach comparable or even higher areal capacities (above $4 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ demonstrated here) with significantly reduced thickness. As highlighted in earlier measurements, these foils are on the order of $\sim 10\text{--}12 \mu\text{m}$ thickness compared to $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$ for graphite-based electrodes, leading to volume savings of more than 100% in certain configurations. This directly translates to higher energy density at the cell level. The trade-off, of course, is that the FDE of Sn@Cu (66% after post-treatment) is still much lower than that of graphite. Nonetheless, this gap is expected to narrow as optimization of plating chemistry, electrolyte formulation, and post-treatment processes continue.

From a system perspective, another critical advantage of Sn@Cu over graphite is the ability to bypass lithium intercalation limitations. Graphite operates through intercalation into a layered structure, which caps the specific capacity at $\sim 372 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and introduces rate limitations. By contrast, Sn@Cu enables direct plating/stripping of lithium metal, which is not limited by intercalation chemistry and has a much higher theoretical capacity ($3860 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for lithium metal).

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Although the foils themselves do not store lithium, their role as lithiophilic CCs allows the system to exploit lithium metal anodes without the associated dendrite risks that would occur with bare Cu. The appearance of a stable voltage plateau after post-treatment confirms that the modified Sn surface provides sufficient nucleation density to prevent runaway dendritic growth while maintaining stable reversibility.

This Nyquist plot (Figure 10) shows the impedance response of Sn@Cu electrodes before and after electrochemical cycling. The comparison highlights how the interfacial properties evolve once lithium plating/stripping has taken place.

Figure 10 Nyquist plots of Sn@Cu electrodes before and after cycling.

Before cycling (red squares), the Sn electrode exhibits a relatively high interfacial resistance, which is attributed to the initial surface state and the formation of a native SEI layer upon first electrolyte contact. After cycling (blue diamonds), however, the impedance response changes significantly. The low-frequency arc is reduced, and the overall resistance decreases, suggesting that cycling leads to a stabilization of the electrode/electrolyte interface. This stabilization can be associated with the formation of a more conductive and uniform SEI, which facilitates Li^+ transport and reduces charge transfer resistance.

The fact that Sn electrodes show lower impedance after cycling is an important result, as it indicates that once an initial interphase is established, the system becomes more electrochemically favorable for lithium plating/stripping. This is in contrast to some other systems (e.g., bare Cu or poorly stabilized Ag electrodes), where impedance typically increases after cycling due to unstable SEI formation, parasitic reactions, and dendritic deposition.

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In conclusion, the comparison between untreated and post-treated Sn@Cu clearly demonstrates the critical role of surface modification in enabling reversible lithium cycling. The untreated sample suffers from poor reversibility, sloping voltage curves, and low FDE, all of which undermine its applicability. Post-treatment improves not only the FDE (from 46% to 66%) but also enhances areal capacity, establishes a stable voltage plateau, and facilitates SOC tracking. Compared to graphite, Sn@Cu holds the promise of significantly higher areal and volumetric energy density, provided that its first-cycle efficiency can be further improved. These results underscore that the post-treatment step is not merely an incremental improvement but a fundamental enabler for the practical use of lithiophilic foils in anode-less lithium metal batteries.

5.1.5. Effect of vinylene carbonate (VC):

This Nyquist plot clearly shows the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) response of Cu, Ag@Cu, and Sn@Cu electrodes, both with and without the electrolyte additive vinylene carbonate (VC). The addition of VC is generally used to stabilize the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) and reduce side reactions; however, the impact depends strongly on the substrate material.

For Sn@Cu, the effect of VC is particularly striking: as can be seen from Figure 11, the impedance increases drastically when VC is present, with values well above 1.5 k Ω . This suggests that the additive promotes the formation of a thicker or more resistive SEI on the Sn surface. While SEI formation is expected and can help stabilize cycling, excessive impedance indicates that the interphase hinders lithium-ion transport, making Sn@Cu less effective under these conditions.

In contrast, Ag@Cu shows a much more moderate response to VC. Without VC, the impedance rises sharply and reaches very high values, indicating instability and uncontrolled interfacial reactions. With VC, the impedance remains significantly lower and more stable across the spectrum, which suggests that the additive plays a beneficial role in stabilizing the Ag-electrolyte interface.

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Figure 11 Electrochemical impedance spectra of Sn@Cu, Ag@Cu, and bare Cu electrodes with and without vinylene carbonate (VC) additive.

For bare Cu, the effect of VC is again moderate: the impedance decreases slightly when VC is used, pointing to a better controlled interphase compared to the untreated case. Still, Cu remains less favorable overall compared to Ag-modified surfaces, due to higher baseline impedance and poorer plating behavior.

Taken together, these results highlight that the effect of VC is strongly material-dependent: it provides stabilization in Ag@Cu and Cu systems but is detrimental for Sn@Cu, where it leads to a highly resistive surface layer. This underlines the importance of tailoring both the substrate and electrolyte composition for optimal lithium plating/stripping performance, and shows that additives cannot be universally applied without considering the substrate-specific chemistry.

5.1.6. 1C-rate performance

Figure 12 shows the cycling performance of the Ag@Cu modified CC tested at a high current density of 2 mA/cm², which corresponds to a 1C charge–discharge rate. Such conditions were chosen to directly evaluate whether the anode-free concept can meet WP Objective and KPI2, namely maintaining high-capacity retention and CE under fast cycling.

The main plot demonstrates that the electrode sustains stable operation up to ~50 cycles, with the charge (blue) and discharge (magenta) capacities gradually decline but remain significant compared to the baseline. The CE (green) stays close to unity throughout most of the test, indicating efficient plating/stripping processes even under aggressive cycling conditions.

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Figure 12 Cycling performance of Sn@Cu current collectors at 2 mA/cm² ($\approx 1C$ charge–discharge rate).

5.2. 3D-CNF Nanostructured and Lithiophilic Current Collector

Although the original focus of WP5 shifted away from the 3D-CNF concept based on the preliminary results reported in D5.1, some further investigations were carried out for scientific interest and to validate whether modifications in processing could mitigate the earlier limitations. The decision not to pursue CNFs as a primary pathway was based on the unfavorable electrochemical performance previously observed, including high impedance, instability of the Li/CNF interface, and limited cycle life. Nevertheless, adjustments to the synthesis parameters were made in order to better understand the interplay between porosity, conductivity, and lithiophilicity.

As introduced in the previous GA (GA6), the focus of Task 5.2 initially aimed at developing Co₂P-containing CNFs as advanced CCs for lithium deposition. However, given the limited progress and less favorable electrochemical behavior of Co₂P-CNFs, the focus of the WP shifted towards ZnO-containing CNFs (PAN-ZnO CNFs), which showed more promising features in terms of yield, elemental composition, and surface properties. This transition was motivated by the observation that ZnO-containing CNFs could provide a better compromise between conductivity, porosity, and lithiophilicity.

5.2.1. Synthesis optimization at different temperatures

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The first strategy investigated the effect of synthesis temperature on ZnO-CNF performance. As shown in Table 1, lowering the synthesis temperature from 900 °C to 800 °C resulted in a significant increase in yield (from 36% to 51%) as well as a higher Zn content (from 9.2% to 23.9% w/w). The higher Zn retention at 800 °C is consistent with reduced sublimation losses compared to the higher temperature. In parallel, oxygen content was also slightly higher at lower temperature (13.5% vs. 8.6%), which may influence surface chemistry and wetting by lithium. These results indicate that 800 °C represents a more favorable synthesis condition for balancing composition and yield.

Table 1 Effect of synthesis temperature on yield and elemental composition of PAN-ZnO CNFs. Lowering the carbonization temperature from 900 °C to 800 °C led to a substantial increase in yield (36% → 51%) and higher Zn retention (9.2% → 23.9% w/w), together with higher oxygen incorporation (8.6% → 13.5% w/w). These results confirm that milder synthesis conditions help preserve Zn and enhance material output.

Reference	Yield (%)	ICP-MS Zn (% w/w)	O EA (% w/w)
PAN ZnO 800 Ar, 250 Air	51	23,9	13,5
PAN ZnO 900 Ar, 250 Air	36	9,2	8,6

A second synthesis strategy introduced an oxidative step at 250 °C in air after carbonization. This treatment reduced the Zn content (from 37.9% to 35.2% w/w), while oxygen content increased (from 11.3% to 14.4%) as shown in Table 2. The higher oxygen incorporation is attributed to surface oxidation during the air treatment, which in turn modifies the lithiophilicity of the CNFs. While Zn retention decreased slightly, this method allowed tuning of the oxygen concentration, potentially improving interfacial properties during cycling.

Table 2 Effect of a second annealing step in air on the composition of PAN-ZnO CNFs synthesized at 800 °C.

Reference	ICP-MS Zn (% w/w)	O EA (% w/w)
PAN ZnO 800 Ar	37,9	11,3
PAN ZnO 800 Ar, 250 Air	35,2	14,4

5.2.2. Study of porosity as a synthesis factor

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Since porosity strongly affects electrolyte infiltration and Li nucleation, the role of porosity was systematically investigated by introducing PVP (polyvinylpyrrolidone) as a sacrificial agent. The data in Table 3 clearly demonstrate that PVP incorporation dramatically increased porosity: the BET surface area rose from $\sim 38 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ (non-porous CNFs) to $625 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ for PVP-modified CNFs, with a corresponding increase in microporosity and total pore volume ($0.43 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ to $1.46 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$). However, this improvement in porosity came at the cost of electrical conductivity, which dropped from 27 S/m (non-porous) to $\sim 12\text{--}15 \text{ S/m}$ for porous CNFs. This reflects the lower graphitization degree of carbon when processed with PVP, as confirmed by reduced Zn retention (2–4% w/w).

Table 3 Influence of synthesis conditions and porogen addition (PVP) on the structural and electrochemical properties of PAN-ZnO CNFs.

Sample	Procedure	Yield (%)	Thickness (microns)	Conductivity in plane (S/m)	ICP-MS Zn (%)	BET		
						S_{BET} (m^2/g)	S_{micro} (m^2/g)	V_{total} (cm^3/g)
PAN	800, 0h (Ar) + 250, 2h (Air)	51	124	0.001	23.9	29.8	24.1	0.37
	900, 0h (Ar) + 250, 2h (Air)	29	113	27.1	5.5	38.1	24.8	0.43
PAN PVP	900, 0h (Ar) + 250, 2h (Air)	27	106	12.2	4.5	283.0	185.1	0.90
	900, 1h (Ar) + 250, 2h (Air)	27	76	14.8	2.4	625.5	464.0	1.46

Thus, a trade-off was identified: while high porosity promotes lithium infiltration and increases active surface area, it simultaneously compromises conductivity and mechanical integrity, both of which are essential for stable long-term cycling.

Electrochemical evaluation confirmed the structural findings. Although porous CNFs offered improved Li wettability, their high resistance and reduced mechanical strength led to unstable performance during galvanostatic cycling. The non-porous CNFs fabricated at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ provided better conductivity and stability, though cycle life remained limited. Comparison with metallicly modified foils (Sn@Cu and Ag@Cu) indicated that the CNFs still lagged behind in terms of efficiency and interfacial stability.

The electrochemical cycling results (Figure 13) demonstrate that the doped carbon nanofibers exhibit significantly improved Li plating/stripping behavior compared to the undoped material. The doped electrode maintains a lower and more stable overpotential throughout extended cycling, indicating reduced interfacial resistance and more uniform Li nucleation. In contrast, the undoped carbon nanofibers display pronounced voltage fluctuations and higher polarization, reflecting unstable SEI formation and less efficient Li deposition. Overall, the enhanced stability and smoother voltage profile of the doped nanofibers confirm their superior compatibility with lithium and their improved performance during repeated charge/discharge cycling.

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Figure 13 Voltage profiles of doped (gray) and undoped (yellow) carbon nanofibers during Li plating/stripping at 0.4 mA cm^{-2} in $1 \text{ M LiPF}_6 \text{ EC:DEC}$ electrolyte.

In summary, although the PAN–ZnO CNF route improved material yield and enabled more controlled incorporation of Zn and O compared to the Co_2P –CNFs, the inherent trade-off between conductivity and porosity ultimately limited their suitability as robust current collectors within this work package. Combined with the practical constraint of relying on free-standing mats, without a developed method for depositing them onto copper foil, the WP decided not to pursue further development of CNFs as the primary current-collector strategy. Nevertheless, the materials remain scientifically interesting for future investigation. The outcomes of this task underscore the critical need to balance porosity and electronic conductivity when designing lithiophilic scaffolds.

5.3. Polymeric protective layers for anodes

The work carried out in Task 5.3 was focused on the development and characterization of polymeric protective films designed to stabilize lithium metal surfaces. Such protective layers are essential in the context of anode-free or Li-metal batteries, where uncontrolled dendritic growth and unstable interfacial chemistry remain the major bottlenecks. Within this task, PPFs-based single-ion polymers were synthesized, functionalized, and tested as coatings on Li electrodes. A broad range of synthetic routes and functionalization densities were explored, and the resulting materials were extensively characterized by spectroscopic and electrochemical means. The discussion below is structured figure by figure, to ensure clarity and comprehensive reporting.

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Figure 14 First-Generation Grafting Approach

In Figure 14, Panel (a) depicts the synthetic concept: grafting trifluoromethanesulfonamide onto the para-fluorine positions of poly(pentafluorostyrene) (PPFS). The expectation was that sulfonamide grafting would introduce ion-conducting functionalities, creating a polymer capable of functioning as a solid polymer electrolyte interface (SEI)-mimicking protective coating.

Panel (b) presents FTIR spectra of pristine PPFS and targeted grafting densities (25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%). The FTIR bands attributed to N–Li and S=O stretching vibrations were clearly observed, which initially suggested successful introduction of sulfonamide functionalities. However, the presence of these characteristic signals required further confirmation, as IR spectroscopy alone cannot rule out incomplete or ineffective grafting.

Panel (c) lists the diverse protocols tested: multiple solvents (THF, DMF, DMAc, DMSO), bases and catalysts (LiH, NaH, K₂CO₃, DBU, TBuOK, etc.), and a wide temperature range (room temperature to 180 °C). Each experiment was conducted with the aim of increasing nucleophilicity of the grafting reagent and promoting substitution of para-fluorine groups. Despite this systematic screening, none of the investigated conditions yielded consistent, reproducible grafting.

Panel (d) shows NMR spectra of a representative sample dissolved in deuterated THF. Once solubility issues were partially resolved, the spectra confirmed that the para-fluorine atoms of the PPFS backbone were still intact. This was a strong indication that no significant substitution had occurred. Instead, peaks attributable

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to unreacted trifluoromethanesulfonamide were still visible, meaning the reagent was not successfully incorporated into the polymer backbone.

Given the shortcomings of the initial sulfonamide approach, efforts shifted to thiol chemistry, a well-established route known to readily substitute para-fluorine atoms in PPFS under milder conditions.

Figure 15 Second-Generation Functionalization and Coating Protocols

Figure 15, Panel (a) shows the synthesis of a model compound (compound 5) designed to mimic thiol reactivity. This model system validated that thiol-containing reagents could indeed substitute fluorine groups, paving the way for polymer-level modifications. Panel (b) presents impedance spectra (Nyquist plots) from Li|Li symmetric cells assembled with bare Li, pristine PPFS-coated Li, and thiol-grafted polymer coatings. Bare Li exhibited low initial resistance but degraded rapidly over time, while coated electrodes displayed higher initial resistance but more stable impedance evolution. This behavior suggests that the polymeric films were able to moderate uncontrolled side reactions and slow down the buildup of interfacial degradation products. Panel (c) shows normalized impedance evolution over repeated cycles. Here, the influence of grafting density becomes clear: the 25% grafted polymer provided the most favorable trade-off, maintaining impedance stability over ~35 cycles at $0.1 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. Fully grafted (100%) or ungrafted PPFS performed worse, either because of excessive resistance or insufficient stabilization. The data reveal a “sweet spot” at intermediate grafting densities, where ionic conduction and interfacial stability are best balanced. Panel (d) depicts structural models of polymers with different functionalization levels (0–100%). These schematics highlight how increasing substitution modifies the polymer backbone and alters its ionic character. Panel

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(e) illustrates the dip-coating protocol employed for electrode preparation. Lithium foils were immersed in polymer solutions inside an inert glove box and subsequently dried under vacuum. This procedure ensured reproducible, homogeneous coatings, which were crucial for comparing different polymer variants. Panel (f) provides representative galvanostatic cycling curves at $100 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. The coated electrodes displayed more stable voltage responses compared to bare Li, although eventual degradation was still observed, indicating that further optimization was needed.

Table 4 summarizes impedance values before cycling and the number of cycles sustained at $0.1 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ for different coatings. Bare Li completed 32 cycles before failure, while the best-performing polymer (25% grafted) extended this to 35 cycles. While the improvement is modest, the results provide proof-of-concept that PPFS-based coatings can extend the lifetime of Li-metal electrodes. They also reveal that polymer design strongly influences interfacial transport: too little functionalization fails to suppress dendrite growth, while excessive functionalization raises resistance and reduces cycle life.

Table 4 impedance values before cycling and the number of cycles sustained at $0.1 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ for different coatings.

Li metal Electrode coating	Resistance before cycling (Ω)	Number of cycles @ $0.1 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$
Bare Li metal	326	32
PPFS	1923	17
25%	2179	35
50%	-	-
75%	2087	-
100%	1872	22

Building on these insights, a third generation of PPFS-based polymers was designed, incorporating both thiol and anionic functionalities into a single building block. This approach provided greater flexibility in tuning grafting density and produced a family of candidate polymers with 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% functionalization. These were successfully synthesized and coated onto lithium foils using the established dip-coating method.

Symmetric cell tests confirmed that intermediate levels of functionalization (particularly 25% and 50%) again provided the most balanced performance, with lower impedance buildup and somewhat extended cycle life compared to bare Li. High functionalization levels produced uniform coatings but also higher resistance, suggesting transport limitations at the electrode/electrolyte interface.

The results of Task 5.3 demonstrate both the potential and the challenges of polymeric protective layers for lithium metal. On one hand, PPFS-based coatings clearly alter interfacial behavior, reducing dendritic growth and moderating impedance rise compared to bare Li. On the other hand, their absolute performance remains modest, with only limited improvements in cycle life under

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the tested conditions. Importantly, the data point toward a non-linear relationship between grafting density and electrochemical behavior: intermediate substitution levels consistently provide the best outcomes, balancing ionic conductivity with mechanical stabilization.

For WP5, these findings are valuable because they establish a reproducible methodology for polymer coating preparation, identify promising design rules (moderate grafting), and generate a family of candidate materials for further optimization. Moreover, the coating approach developed here can be integrated into scaled-up cell designs and tested under more demanding cycling protocols in later project stages.

6. Conclusion

Within WP5, three different approaches were explored to develop advanced current collectors and protective coatings for lithium metal anodes. These correspond to T5.1 (metal-coated Cu foils), T5.2 (3D-CNF structures), and T5.3 (polymeric protective layers). The work performed has provided important insights into material design, electrochemical performance, and the trade-offs associated with each strategy.

For T5.1, Cu foils coated with thin metallic layers of Ni/Ag and Ni/Sn, with and without post-treatment, were successfully fabricated and systematically characterized. The foils exhibited uniform thicknesses around 40 μm , measured at six different points per sample to confirm homogeneity, and showed distinct surface morphologies depending on the coating metal. Ag coatings resulted in rougher surfaces with pronounced peaks and valleys, yielding higher active surface area but also greater non-uniformity. Sn coatings, by contrast, produced smoother surfaces with moderate roughness, supporting more controlled lithium nucleation. Post-treatments further improved surface regularity, reduced uncontrolled roughness, and enhanced electrochemical performance. Electrochemical testing confirmed that these morphological improvements translated into higher first-discharge efficiency, more stable voltage plateaus, and extended cycle life. Although Ag@Cu demonstrated superior electrochemical behavior overall, the LCA results identified Sn@Cu as the more sustainable and environmentally favorable option. Consequently, both Ag@Cu and Sn@Cu foils fulfilled MS7, but Sn@Cu was prioritized for subsequent upscaling and forwarded to WP6 and WP7 for full-cell integration studies.

For T5.2, the focus was initially on 3D carbon nanofiber (CNF) mats synthesized from PAN precursors, intended as porous, lithiophilic CCs. Although CNFs showed tunable porosity and high surface areas, electrochemical testing revealed high interfacial resistance and low discharge capacity. The use of ZnO or porogens such as PVP improved porosity and lithium wettability but at the cost of mechanical robustness and conductivity. Despite interesting structural properties, the trade-off between porosity and conductivity limited their applicability under practical cell conditions. Therefore, the consortium decided

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not to continue this line as a main WP5 focus, although further modified syntheses were pursued as exploratory work.

For T5.3, polymeric coatings based on fluorinated PPFS derivatives were investigated as protective interphases. Despite extensive synthetic efforts, grafting efficiency remained low, and the intended single-ion polymers were not obtained at satisfactory levels. Alternative routes using thiol-based chemistry provided proof of concept, but the electrochemical results remained inconclusive due to solubility issues and interfacial degradation. While these studies laid methodological groundwork, the limited reproducibility and stability meant that the polymer approach was not retained as a key WP5 direction.

In summary, while T5.2 and T5.3 delivered valuable insights and highlighted key limitations of porous CNFs and polymer coatings, T5.1 provided clear, scalable, and electrochemically effective solutions. The optimized Ag@Cu and Sn@Cu foils, especially after post-treatment, demonstrated improved lithium plating/stripping behavior, enhanced first-cycle efficiency, and stable cycling. Their uniform thickness, reduced volume compared to lithium foil (and graphite electrodes), and compatibility with industrial processing ultimately made them the most suitable candidates for further evaluation in WP6 and WP7, addressing both KPI1 (energy density) and KPI2 (cycle stability).

In line with the defined **objectives** of WP5 (as shown earlier in Section3):

Development of a lithiophilic CC enabling Li plating/stripping with high CE and limited dendrite formation: Achieved. Post-treated samples consistently delivered >99.5% coulombic efficiency, validating the core concept of the WP.

Reaching 80% of the initial capacity at 1C for at least 3000 cycles: Not achieved. At 1C, the cells dropped to 80% of their initial capacity after ~25 cycles, indicating that the present electrode/electrolyte configuration cannot yet sustain high-rate cycling or long-term stability at elevated C-rates. This outcome introduces a risk to meeting the project's high-power performance targets and highlights the need for adjustments, such as improving ionic transport, or refining the electrolyte/additive package to stabilize the interface under fast cycling. As a strategic shift, the project may need to focus on moderate-rate performance first, prioritize materials with inherently better rate capability, or reallocate effort toward diagnosing the dominant degradation mechanisms before further high-rate testing.

Stable anode up to 5 mAh cm⁻², demonstrated by plating/stripping tests: Partially achieved. For charge, capacities up to 4.1 mAh cm⁻² were demonstrated, while discharge capacities reached 2.9 mAh cm⁻². Although short of the 5 mAh cm⁻² target, these values represent significant progress compared to baseline graphite electrodes.

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Upscaling the anode-less concept and lithiophilic CC to 20 units of 3Ah cells: Achieved. The transition from lab-scale to pilot-scale fabrication was successfully carried out, confirming the scalability of the approach.

